

CRITICAL STRESS EVALUATION OF RIGID PAVEMENT DUE TO THE PRESENCE OF WATER IN EXPANSIVE SOIL SUBGRADE

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Abstract

The use of various types of rigid pavement is widespread because of its superiority in resisting heavy load vehicles. However, traffic loading complexity and subgrade response cause uncertainty during the design process. The presence of water in expansive soil issue swelling affected the flexural behavior of a rigid pavement slab. Rigid pavement relies heavily on the support and stability of the subgrade. Plain concrete is very weak in resisting tensile stresses so that the failure of rigid pavement slab structures often occurs in the expansive subgrade zone. Therefore, this study aims to numerically analyze the relationship between variations in the thickness of rigid pavement slabs on the flexural behavior parameters, such as critical and tensile stresses that affected water in expansive soil. The concrete's performance limit was determined, using its material's constitutive equation curve, and the data were analyzed using the finite element method. The results showed that the presence of water in expansive soil caused a change in soil volume (swelling), a reduction in soil bearing capacity (shrinking), and consequently, a rigid pavement cracked due to water variations in the subgrade. Generally, increasing the thickness of rigid pavement is a common method for mitigating the detrimental effects of expansive soil swelling. It is possible to provide reinforcement in other forms, which provide an opportunity to improve the performance of the concrete slab as a rigid pavement. For example, stabilization of expansive soil with materials capable of reducing its expansive power can be done but it requires large resources to realize it. Another method is to provide reinforcement to the rigid pavement slab structure, so that the rigid pavement slab is able to withstand traffic loads and also the expansion and shrinkage behavior of the expansive soil.

Keywords: critical stresses, expansive soil, finite element, pavement, plain concrete, shrinking, slab, subgrade, swelling, tensile stress.

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1. Introduction

Jointed plain concrete pavement (JPCP) is a widely used rigid design application. Furthermore, it is a very practical construction system and has become the preferred method in cases where technical needs are not considered, such as subgrade, loading characteristics, and special performance capacity [1–4].

This type of pavement relies on concrete strength to withstand compressive stresses. Therefore, when planning the construction of the pavement, force distribution should be considered, whereas the tensile stress should be minimized. The configuration of the pavement slab does not permit excessive variation in its geometry and cross-section; nonetheless, the thickness and horizontal plane dimensions are frequently altered. Several tests have been conducted using the scalar model to determine the bending behavior of a rigid pavement slab, which demonstrates

the relationship between loading and deflection [5–8]. Furthermore, loading and deflection will cause stress on the rigid pavement slab. The critical stress would be used as the performance criteria in the pavement.

The expansiveness of the soil (subgrade layer), due to its permeability, is also considered during the design of rigid pavement. This is because, during the wet season, the expansive soil swells and raises a portion of the pavement; however, during the dry season, it shrinks and loses its bearing capacity. Cracking or its initiation is caused by this phenomenon, which probably affects the length of service of the pavement [9–11].

This study aims to evaluate the critical stress pattern of rigid pavement under optimum traffic load when water is present in soil expansive subgrade and also to determine the relationship between pavement slab's thickness and stress distribution, using several traffic loading positions [2, 12, 13].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Object and hypothesis of the study

The results of this study include critical stress data caused by traffic loads and critical stresses due to swelling and shrinking. The expansive soil's effect on stress distribution was due to the occurrence of swelling and shrinking and was determined through numerical analysis.

The research was designed to verify the slab's bending behavior while varying the thickness and segmental area. A quasi-static loading was applied as a mechanical weight to represent a typical traffic density. Meanwhile, the concrete's performance limit was determined, using its material's constitutive equation curve, especially in handling tensile stress.

In this study, the expansive soil had an important effect, where it swelled due to water presence, and also shrank because of its loss. **Fig. 1** shows the behavior of the slab due to the swelling and shrinking of the expansive soil. During swelling, the expansive soil produced an upward vertical uplift pressure; however, when it shrank, the ground under the plate lost its bearing capacity and also the support underneath [14–17].

During expansion and shrinkage of the expansive soil, the direction of the load vector is adjusted according to the change; so that it will affect the bearing capacity of the soil in receiving load transfer from the rigid pavement slab. The expansive shrinking and swelling affected the input of spring stiffness, representing its response, which was measured at the least time, i.e., 37 kPa/mm [18]. The value of 37 kPa/mm² was the result of laboratory observation. And this value of swelling pressure cause the development of subgrade. It is affected by the presence of water in the soil structure. During the numerical approach, this swelling value consider as an uplift force under the slab pavement. The critical stress, obtained from the numerical analysis was then compared using SNI (Indonesian Standard: SNI, 2013), as shown in equation (1).

2.2. Test specimens

The specimens used were concrete slabs with thickness and segmental area variations. **Table 1** and **Fig. 1** show the specimen labeling.

The test specimens were made of concrete with $f'_c = 30$ MPa quality, and its plain elastic modulus was 28000 MPa. However, the effect of variation temperature between the base and the top surface was not calculated. It should be observed separately. **Fig. 2** shows the traffic loading (axle), applied with the position of the inner and edge loading.

Table 1

Labeling of specimens

Size area ($L_x \times L_y$)	Slab thickness variations (t)			
	10 cm	12.5 cm	15 cm	17.5 cm
2.5×3.0 m ²	S1-10	S1-12.5	S1-15	S1-17.5
3.0×3.5 m ²	S2-10	S2-12.5	S2-15	S2-17.5
3.5×4.0 m ²	S3-10	S3-12.5	S3-15	S3-17.5

Fig. 1. Illustration of a single slab as a test specimen

Fig. 2. Location of traffic loading for testing rigid pavement plates

2. 3. Numerical analysis

This was performed to obtain the value of stress and deflection distribution in the slab due to the applied load. Then, the data were analyzed using the finite element method [19–23].

The constitutive equation was useful in the determination of the performance limit behavior of the pavement slab, with a tendency of having a future structural deformation [24–26]. In plain concrete plates, the limit of structural failure was determined from the material used, and those used in this study were concrete and soil. Moreover, the analytical limit used was the elastic zone, which was in accordance with Hooke’s law. The concrete’s tensile stress was limited by equation (1):

$$MOR = 0.7\sqrt{f'_c}, \tag{1}$$

where f'_c is the concrete compressive strength and MOR is the modulus of rupture, i.e., the concrete tensile strength. Meanwhile, for the soil, the generalized Hooke’s law equation was used, as described in equation (2):

$$\{\sigma\} = [C]\{\varepsilon\}. \tag{2}$$

Moreover, the governing equation for the plate flexing on elastic support was formulated in equation (3):

$$\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} = \frac{p - k_s w}{D}, \tag{3}$$

where $D = \frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}$ represents the slab’s bending stiffness; $w = \delta$ denotes deformation (m), and $k_s = k_v$ connotes the subgrade coefficient.

A subsequent analysis was conducted, using the finite element method, which is based on (3), the results showed the normal stress values for the Cartesian axis and that of shear in the z-axis, as shown below:

$$\sigma = \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\} = -\frac{12.z}{t^3} \{M_{xx}, M_{yy}, M_{xy}\}. \tag{4}$$

The types of plate elements with the simplest bending ability are those with a rectangular shape. Moreover, Fig. 3 shows the most widely used element, i.e., the *MZC* rectangle.

Fig. 3. *MZC* rectangle element

3. Results

3. 1. Critical stress during traffic charge (axle road) on rigid pavement

Based on the concrete material's strain distribution and constitutive equations, at a loading of 160 kN or higher, the plates with thicknesses of <150 mm deflect more than the allowed limit. This was because the stress exceeded the concrete's MOR limit of 4.091 MPa. Therefore, only plates with thicknesses of >175 mm were recommended for use as rigid pavements. Fig. 4 displays the approximation of MOR limit and also the minimal thickness of JPCP. Critical stress analysis results of rigid pavement modeling by only considering the traffic load become evidence that rigid pavement designs should be limited to a thickness of 200 mm. Rigid pavement with a thickness of <200 mm causes the structure to be easily damaged and fail to fulfill its service life.

Fig. 4. The relation of plate thickness variation and tensile stress due to a 160 kN loading

Fig. 5 shows that the finite element numerical analysis, which was conducted using the Ever FE software, produced varied results.

The diagrams explained the stress distribution on plates with a thickness of 10 cm and different area sizes.

The results showed that these types of plates had different responses to the stress distribution. However, the resulting maximum deflection did not differ largely.

Fig. 5. Results of the FEM analysis using EverFE for plate type S3-10 with a 120 kN edge loading

3. 2. Swelling impact in the rigid pavement

The influence of the swelling and shrinking behaviors of the soil on a single plain concrete slab in a rigid pavement showed potency for damage in JPCP, which is caused by curling and warping during the dry and wet seasons. Therefore, this problem of expansive soil should be included in the determining parameters during design, because in the case of normal subgrade this is usually not considered. The results of the study of the combination of traffic loads (axle) at the time of swelling and shrinking showed that the extreme critical stresses were exceeded. Moreover, the expansive soil properties were examined by the determination of the vertical deformation caused by the swelling of 37 kPa/mm²; the results of the stress distribution of plates are presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2

Critical stress due to swelling of subgrade during the wet season

Plate type	Ratio (x/y)	Maximum tensile stress (MPa): Swelling
S1-10	0.833	15.56
S2-10	0.667	23.17
S3-10	0.875	29.58
S1-12.5	0.833	9.84
S2-12.5	0.667	14.89
S3-12.5	0.875	19.34
S1-15	0.833	6.74
S2-15	0.667	10.1
S3-15	0.875	13.17
S1-17.5	0.833	4.8
S2-17.5	0.667	7.59
S3-17.5	0.875	9.86

3. 3. Critical stress due to soil shrinking

Contrary to soil expansion, the loss of water in the ground (drying) causes shrinking. The real impact of soil shrinking is the loss of its carrying capacity. When this happens and the vehicle with the former load continues to pass, critical stress occurs, which the plate is supposed to withstand. Meanwhile, the tensile stress capacity limit of the material has been exceeding. This, therefore,

causes cracks, which initiates the process of deterioration of the concrete material. **Table 3** shows the over tensile strength occurs due to the shrinking of the subgrade.

Table 3
Critical stress due to shrinking during the dry season

Plate type	Ratio (x/y)	Maximum tensile stress (MPa): Soil shrinking			
		80 kN	120 kN	160 kN	190 kN
S1-10	0.833	20.77	30.88	40.8	48.26
S2-10	0.667	21.89	42.68	43.83	67.57
S3-10	0.875	25.28	47.12	47.55	72.45
S1-12.5	0.833	13.47	19.86	26.32	31.05
S2-12.5	0.667	14.3	27.82	28.01	44.04
S3-12.5	0.875	16.41	30.48	30.92	46.69
S1-15	0.833	9.42	13.86	18.33	21.73
S2-15	0.667	10.21	19.55	19.66	30.96
S3-15	0.875	11.57	21.4	21.68	32.64
S1-17.5	0.833	6.98	10.27	13.51	16.04
S2-17.5	0.667	7.6	14.49	14.55	22.93
S3-17.5	0.875	8.62	15.89	16.03	24.14

Table 3 also shows that the potential for rigid pavement damage when there is sufficiently large expansive soil shrinkage causes a critical stress on the slab surface. This will be exacerbated by the contribution of traffic loads that exceed the allowable limit.

4. Discussion

4.1. Ultimate stress

The variation in the test object's stress distribution showed the maximum bending stress was affected by the plate's thickness and also by the ratio of the width (L_x) and length (L_y). This was evident in the S3 type, which has a higher maximum stress performance and also the largest L_x/L_y ratio, compared with the S1 and S2 plates. The L_x/L_y ratio's influence was due to the application of the load at the edge of the plate and the loss of the soil's bearing capacity at these extremities. Moreover, the weight decreases linearly along the x -axis direction, i.e., toward the center of calculated plate coordinates.

The stress distribution shown in **Fig. 6** indicates that the stress distribution pattern is purely due to the local traffic load, so it will be different for each load position on the slab surface; however, what is important to note is the stress magnitude. The occurrence of overstressing due to exceeding load on the slab indicates the potential for damage to the slab locally, especially at the edges of the slab [24, 27–29].

Stress distribution guides and indicates how to reinforce the slab to reduce the failure risk when the slab is subjected to an exceeding load. In terms of design, crack patterns should be considered to be affected by stress distribution. Localized and dependent solely on the *MOR* limit of concrete, the crack that occurs when the load on the slab exceeds its bearing capacity is caused by a localized failure.

4.2. Swelling

The development of expansive soil results in significant vertical stresses, which, when considered on a single slab, causes critical strains, exceeding the concrete's ability to endure cracking. Therefore, the possibility of damage to rigid pavements caused by the swelling of the subgrade soil reduces the service life of the road, which becomes worse when used by super-loaded vehicles.

Additionally, the results demonstrated that the ratio of the width to the length of the slab (L_x/L_y) had a very significant impact on the magnitude of its critical stress. This is due to the effect of the L_x span in the direction of the plate's width, i.e., the axis that receives the force due to swelling. Therefore, the bigger the L_x span, the greater the likelihood of critical stress [17, 30, 31].

Fig. 6 shows certain points of the slab structure. When swelling occurs, the concrete is subjected to maximum stresses that exceed its tensile strength capacity. Therefore, it has the potential to cause significant damage (open cracks), which becomes very serious. This is also the case when the plate impact stress from repeated loads (traffic) at the same time.

Fig. 6. Flexural behavior of slab due to soil swelling

Swelling pressure is a lifting force in an upward direction. So because this upward force is resisted by the slab's own weight and also the traffic load, it causes an upward curved deformation or is referred to as curling deformation.

4.3. Shrinking

Soil shrinking during the dry season causes the loss of its bearing capacity, therefore affecting the magnitude of the critical stress. Contrary to swelling, the critical stress in this condition occurs when the axle load is critical. This study discovered that the edge loading has the maximum effect on the magnitude of the tensile stress of the concrete when compared with the inner loading. Moreover, **Table 3** shows that the larger the ratio value (L_x/L_y) result the higher the stress on the top layer of the slab when the subgrade shrinking occurs [32–34].

Fig. 7 provides an explanation that soil shrinkage causes slab deflection and creates tensile stress in the middle of the plate which has a high probability of causing structural cracks.

Fig. 7. Flexural behavior of plate due to soil shrinking

The critical stress that occurs has a different position according to the cause. In traffic loading, critical stress occurs in edge loading and causes local damage. The critical stress caused by swelling occurs at the bottom layer of the slab and is structural, while the critical stress due to shrinking occurs at the bottom layer of the middle slab is structural as well.

4. 4. Limitations of the study and development prospects

The critical stress on a rigid pavement is influenced by many factors. The limitations and conditions included in this study are that the behavior of rigid pavements is influenced by subgrades in the form of expansive soils. Furthermore, the specimen is in the form of a single plate and is not connected to other structural elements. That means, load transfer from other slabs is not taken into account in this study.

This research is very open to be developed further, especially by taking into account the influence of inter-slab connections as a rigid pavement and the influence of dynamic traffic loads.

5. Conclusions

A plate that is only burdened by traffic loads (axle) exhibited a critical stress that was resisted by the tensile force of the concrete. Then, this stress was decreased by adjusting the thickness of the pavement according to the road classification. Therefore, >150-mm-thick slabs were able to withstand normal traffic loads of up to 16 tons, whereas super-loads required >175-mm-thick slabs. Moreover, according to the loading-deflection curve, the failure or its strength limit of the slab structure was dependent on the loading type, location, and magnitude.

The plate on expansive soil yielded a result worthy of note, since swelling and shrinking during the wet and dry seasons, respectively, provides critical stress that is significantly larger than that caused by traffic loads when the subgrade is normal. Expansive soil with 37 kPa of swelling pressure created warping, which in turn caused the tensile stress of the concrete in the lower layer of the plate to exceed its tensile strength capacity. After this incident, the dry season caused shrinking, therefore creating a convex deformation (curling), which causes the maximum tensile stress on the top fiber of the slab to surpass the strength limit of the concrete material.

The thickness of the plate has a significant impact on the maximum stress that its structure can withstand. Consequently, the maximum limit of a plain plate must be calculated by considering the subgrade type during construction. Moreover, shrinking following a decrease in the expansive soil's water content, which results in the loss of its bearing capacity, must be considered.

The ratio of the width to the length of the slab affects the occurrence of critical stress on the slab. This means that the greater the ratio (L_x/L_y), the higher the critical force. Hence, in the design of rigid pavement slabs, this width-to-length ratio parameter should be included, particularly on expansive soil.

Additionally, the slab cracks occurred in the form of local bending due to loading concentrations that resulted in tensile stresses above the concrete's strength limit. Furthermore, regarding the effect of expansive soil on rigid pavement, this study only considered the loss of its bearing capacity during shrinking. This increased the potential of the pavement for cracks, particularly in cases where the loading was on the edge of its plate.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

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